

Strategic Analysis of Coca-Cola: Unveiling Growth Option, STP Framework, and Marketing Mix Strategies

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Abstract— The Coca-Cola Company, a global leader in the beverage industry, has maintained its position in the face of changing market conditions, customer preferences, and competition. This study analyzes Coca-Cola's strategic growth options using tools such as the Ansoff Matrix and Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) framework. It explores various strategies to sustain its competitive advantage, including market penetration, product development, and market development. Through an examination of Coca-Cola's marketing mix, brand equity, and global distribution, this study aims to offer strategic recommendations for enhancing growth and competitiveness in the global beverage market. The research identifies key opportunities for expansion, addresses challenges, and underscores the importance of customized marketing strategies tailored to regional markets.

Keywords: Coca-Cola, Ansoff Matrix, Segmentation, Targeting, Positioning, Growth Strategy, Market Penetration, Product Development, Competitive Advantage

1.0 INTRODUCTION

This study seeks to analyse the present state of Coca-Cola and the overall industry environment, appraise its available assets, and suggest strategic suggestions to maintain ongoing expansion and competitiveness in the worldwide beverage market. This paper will do a thorough study to find potential areas for growth and expansion. It will explore possibilities such as product creation, product extension, or market development, utilising frameworks such as the Ansoff Matrix and Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) analysis. In addition, the article will examine the creation of a customized marketing mix to bolster the selected growth plan and strengthen Coca-Cola's position in the market.

2.0 OVERVIEW OF THE COLA-COLA COMPANY

Cola-Cola, a multinational company, was formed by a pharmacist in Atlanta, United States, between the 18th to 19th centuries. This industry operates in several parts of the world. Their portfolio entails hundreds of brands, which include several drinks like fruit juices, teas, bottled water, beverages, energy drinks, and so on. The company distributes more than 1.9 billion serving drinks in more than 200 countries daily (Business Insider 2011).

In terms of financial performance, Coca-Cola is doing well, achieving at least a 4 percent increase in sales in the last ten years, with over 20 billion US dollars. Coca-Cola's organisation kept on changing as time kept flying in order to adapt to a change in customer preferences and changing market dynamics. Through carrying out new business units

and strategic restructuring, Coca-Cola aims to make an alignment with its strategic focus area towards its operational activities. (Al Tunaiji, 2019). Since its establishment more than 100 years ago, Coca-Cola has passed through times of economic climates, market shifts, and intense competition, yet it is continuing to expand as a global leader in the beverage industry (The Coca-Cola Company n.d).

3.0 ANALYSIS OF GROWTH OPTIONS FOR COCA-COLA

3.1 INTRODUCTION TO GROWTH OPTIONS

In the context of strategic decision-making for firms, growth options play a crucial role, particularly in scenarios where there is uncertainty regarding future market conditions. When a firm possesses a monopoly in both investment opportunities and product markets, the growth option holds minimal strategic significance (Asvanunt et al., 2009). However, when these assumptions are at ease, the importance of growth options becomes more pronounced.

Consider a situation where a company, M, has the chance to make an initial irreversible investment (I) to improve its production efficiency. This investment, akin to purchasing a growth option, lowers future production costs. The random variable, which represents the uncertainty surrounding future demand, influences the decision to invest.

Real options theory suggests that the value of growth options is positively correlated with firm value volatility. Empirical evidence indicates that firms with greater growth options, such as those engaged in R&D activities, exhibit stronger correlations between firm value (Tobin's Q) and stock volatility (Asvanunt et al., 2009). Additionally, the decomposition of volatility into systematic and unsystematic components reveals nuanced effects on firm value. While both components enhance the value of growth options, systematic volatility also affects discount rates, leading to ambiguous overall effects.

3.2 STRATEGIC GROWTH ANALYSIS: MARKET PENETRATION STRATEGIES FOR COCA-COLA USING THE ANSOFF MATRIX

In carrying out strategy management within an organization, the Ansoff matrix is widely implemented. Coca-Cola, as a global company in the beverage industry, gives an overview of the application of the Ansoff framework. This matrix helps carry out an in-depth analysis of any risks associated with each other within an organization (MindTools, n.d.). It is often used along with other tools like SWOT,

PESTEL, and the Porter 5 framework to give a proper analysis to help businesses grow.

Figure 1: 2x2 Table Ansoff Matrix (Stratechi n.d.).

The figure presents four specific growth strategies, which are market penetration, which has to do with the concept of increasing sales of products and services into existing markets. Second, market development emphasises any new market or segment of the market for existing products and services. Third product development, which carries out the focus of bringing about new products or services to existing markets. Lastly, diversification which as to do with coming into a current market alongside new products (Ecobici, 2017). Among the Ansoff matrices that will keep serving as the fundamental development of Coca-Cola is market penetration which aligns with the organization's goal to "refresh the world, inspire moments of optimism, create value, and make a difference." (Barrett et al., 2013, p 3). Coca-Cola aims to be among the top competitors in beverages and continue to sustain its profit by doing everything it can to sell its existing portfolio of beverages in an established market. The company's extensive products, like Sprite and Fanta, serve as a springboard for market penetration initiatives.

Coca-Cola carries out a multifaceted approach to effectively bring out market penetration strategies. First, the company implements its brand equity and global distribution networks in order to stimulate customer demand and amplify marketing efforts. Through the implementation of promotional strategies, advertising campaigns, and strategic pricing, Coca-Cola strives to acquire a substantial portion of consumer preferences in the current markets. Additionally, the industry consistently engaged itself in innovative means to meet up with a change in the preferences of customers and tastes, for instance, they make introduction of Coca-Cola Zero sugar with the aim to support the effort by giving the option of low and no-calorie beverages to maintain a healthy lifestyle toward their customers (Coca-Cola India, n.d.). To ensure sustained growth and relevance, Coca-Cola diversifies its product portfolio within the existing markets.

Collaboration also plays an important role in Coca Cola market penetration endeavours. Collaboration with sports

events, cultural festivals, and restaurants helps to foster consumer engagement and increase the visibility of the brand. Coca-Cola utilizes co-branded promotion and sponsorship deals to enhance its influence and reach within target markets. Additionally, Coca-Cola leverages collaborative efforts in procurement through its Bottlers' Sales and Services division, focusing on driving operational efficiencies and cost control while managing the complexities inherent in a multi-tiered vendor network (Perry, 2024).

Furthermore, Coca-Cola carries out localized marketing initiatives to ensure the cultivation of an in-depth connection with regional customers. Coca-Cola's tailored campaign features cultural references and community-centric events with several audiences and local influencers, thereby strengthening its presence in distinct geographical markets (Growth Strategy n.d.).

Coca-Cola's decision to implement a market penetration strategy is strategically justified when assessed using the Ansoff Matrix. This strategy employs already-established products in existing markets, which is in keeping with Ansoff's premise that it offers a low-risk chance for expansion. Coca-Cola increases its competitive position in the beverage market to maximize revenue and optimize its resources and talents. Empirical studies further indicate that market penetration is a powerful tool to produce improvements in market share as well as increase the success of the organization (Oakley, 2015).

The continuing success of Coca-Cola in marketing penetration is shown by its history of seizing dominant markets and increasing recognition around the globe. The corporation efficiently assures that its brand distribution networks, equity, and global presence make instant penetration of new markets while decreasing the risk of its investment (Oakley, 2015).

4.0 SEGMENTATION, TARGETING AND POSITIONING (STP)

4.1 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF SEGMENTATION, TARGETING, AND POSITIONING (STP)

Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning (STP) is a marketing strategy that carries out the employment of a business with the sole aim of reaching its intended target audience and establishing a vigorous brand identity while customization of marketing endeavors is made in accordance. This STP strategy proves to be beneficial for industries to obtain prosperity in a competitive market and to carry out optimization of their marketing endeavors. Each of the STPs has its own meaning. These segments can be categorized in several ways, such as geography (location), demographics (income, age, and gender), behavioral (usage pattern and brand loyalty), and psychographics (lifestyle, values). (Emkaj, 2023).

Targeting is the next step in the STP model. At this stage, it involves making a selection of one or more selections that align with the goal of the business. The key criteria to implement have to deal with "market potential and size of the selected segments, the competitive landscape within each

segment, alignment with the company's products or services, and accessibility and reachability of the chosen segments" (Emkaj, 2023).

A position which is the final stage is the process of creating a perception or distinct image background of the product towards the minds of the buyers to purchase the product. To adopt a positioning strategy, companies make the identification of "unique attributes or benefits of their product or service, understand how competitors are positioned and find a unique angle, develop compelling messaging and branding that resonates with the target audience, and consistently deliver on the promises made in their positioning." (Emkaj, 2023).

4.2 SEGMENTATION STRATEGY FOR COCA-COLA

The segmentation strategy is essential for Coca-Cola to carry out an analysis to gain insight into the target market as well as the marketing position of the potential customers. There exist four key segments of Coca-Cola which are geographic, demographic, behavioural, and psychographic. Coca-Cola's geographic reach is targeted, expensive, and customer-oriented in several parts of the world, touching urban, suburban, and rural areas. This strategy ensures that Coca-Cola products cover all areas of the world. (Coca-Cola segmentation targeting and positioning n.d.). It was because of this strategy that Coca-Cola expanded its distribution, covering over 200 countries.

Coca-Cola demographics target a broad range of people, which encompass age, family size, and income (Anik, 2020). For instance, it caters to individuals ranging from young consumers aged 10 to older generations up to 40 years old.

Coca-Cola also analyses the behavioural patterns of its customers to understand the product they prefer or need. By doing so, the company gets to understand customer attitudes and responds with a transformed portfolio of suitable products to meet those needs (Coca-Cola segmentation targeting and positioning n.d.).

Lastly, Coca-Cola targets consumers across a wide socio-economic spectrum, focusing on personality traits such as independence, personal growth, and authenticity. Through its marketing efforts, Coca-Cola "basically focuses on the fact that people should think Coke is for all" (Anik 2020, p. 29).

4.3 TARGETING STRATEGY FOR COCA-COLA

Coca-Cola employs special tools to reach diverse marketing categories. This includes the division of the market into particular segments, diversifying several ranges of products, developing sophisticated packaging and branding, targeting large markets, and prioritizing niche marketing (Kotler et al., 2020).

Coca-Cola conducts market segmentation while analyzing demographic, psychographic, and behavioural data to establish discrete consumer groups with special demands and preferences. This segmentation is the ability to customize products and messages to connect effectively among each particular targeted segment.

Coca-Cola's targeting strategy heavily relies on the variety of products being produced. The company produces

several beverages, such as cola sugar-free and diet alternatives, as well as non-cola beverages like portable water. The Coca-Cola product portfolio helps to cater to diverse tastes and preferences among several customer categories. Coca-Cola strategically designs its products to target particular categories of customers, especially the younger generation, who value modern aesthetics and cultural relevance. Coca-Cola aims to foster intense relationships with its audience by bringing about popular personalities and contemporary cultural trends (Coca-Cola Segmentation...n.d).

Coca-Cola uses mass marketing tactics to efficiently target and attract several market segments through the provision of diverse products that cater to a broad spectrum of age groups, lifestyles, and health preferences. In contrast, niche marketing targets certain segments of consumers, such as health-conscious individuals who are ready to allocate a higher budget for organic or natural products (Boardmix, n.d.).

4.4 POSITIONING STRATEGY FOR COCA-COLA

Coca-Cola's positioning approach centres on not only presenting its beverages as refreshments but also triggering celebration, happiness, and positivity. The company has cultivated a deep emotional connection with customers through its continual emphasis on the moment of joy in its advertising campaigns. Consequently, the company brand has had strong tides of revitalization and enjoyment. Coca-Cola's positioning strategy extends beyond its range of products, presenting its image as a lifestyle choice rather than just an option for beverages. By carrying out the positioning strategy, Coca-Cola has established itself as a prominent participant in the market, deeply embedding itself in society and everyday routines as a symbol of pleasure and communal moments (Boardmix n.d).

The segmentation, targeting, and positioning strategy for Coca-Cola have been extensively detailed in the table below.

Market Segmentation	Targeting	Positioning
Geographical Market		Offer Happiness
Region	Locally and internationally	
Density	All areas: urban, suburban, and rural	
Demographic		
Age	Ten to twenty-five years and twenty-five to forty years	
Gender	M/F	
Life-cycle stage	From children to mature people	
Income	High, low, and medium	
Occupation	All occupations	
Behavioural		

Degree of loyalty	Upcoming and total loyalists	
Benefits sought	Get the body refreshed	
Personality	Friendly and outgoing	
Psychographic		
Social class	Citizens of the middle class, young dependents, and upper-class people	

Table 1: (Coca-Cola Segmentation, targeting and positioning, n.d).

5.0 DEVELOPMENT OF MARKETING MIX FOR COCA-COLA

5.1 COMPREHENDING THE MARKETING MIX

The comprehension of the marketing mix entails the adoption of strategies and objectives by organizations to enhance the promotion of their products or brands within the market. The marketing mix has undergone both development and increased importance, originating from the microeconomic theory's notion of price (The Economic Times, n.d). Numerous practitioners and scholars have played a pivotal role in shaping this progression

Neil H. Borden, a distinguished figure in the realm of marketing instruction and investigation, is widely acknowledged for the inception and subsequent proliferation of the phrase "marketing mix" (Borden, 1965). Borden highlighted the dynamic and creative aspect of marketing management, drawing on James Culliton's image of a corporate executive as a "mixer of ingredients."

Borden's initial marketing mix consisted of 12 components, which included product planning, price, branding, distribution methods, personal selling, advertising, promotions, packaging, display, servicing, physical handling, and fact-collection and analysis (Borden, 1965). Later on, experts and professionals improved and broadened this structure, incorporating new components and modifications to adapt to different situations and sectors.

During his seminar work in 1964, McCarthy enhanced the marketing mix notion by combining Borden's 12 parts into four essential components, which are commonly referred to as the 4Ps: product, pricing, promotion, and place (McCarthy, 1964). This framework offered a practical method for converting marketing planning into implementable strategies, assisting managers in making choices concerning their product offers, price strategies, promotional efforts, and distribution networks.

The 4Ps paradigm quickly received extensive recognition, establishing itself as a fundamental aspect of marketing theory and practice (Ridge, 2023). The methodology carries out provision for a well-organized approach to marketing management while allowing the manager to carry out rigorous assessments or to make an

adjustment to their tactical approach based on the evolving market and the demand shift pattern of the consumers.

5.2 INNOVATIVE MARKETING STRATEGIES OF COCA-COLA: A CLOSER LOOK AT THE 4Ps

Coca-Cola raised itself as the best beverage company as it adopted a unique marketing strategy technique. By adopting the marketing mix which is the 4Ps, the company kept on increasing their sales while defeating other competitors.

Figure 2: The 4Ps of the Marketing Mix (Kotler and Armstrong, 2014).

Product: Among all the 4Ps in the marketing mix, the product is the main element since anything that is placed on the market can be able to give the satisfaction of what a man actually needs or wants. Coca-Cola displays several products to the customers in order for them to choose the one that best satisfies their wants. The organization has displayed its capability to fit into a change in demand shift pattern, offering a range of several types of drinks rather than just Coca-Cola Soda. (Statista, 2019). By introducing options such as caffeine-free and diet-cola beverages, the organization demonstrates its attentiveness to consumer well-being (Raghavendra & Renuka, 2018). This diverse product portfolio significantly contributes to Coca-Cola's strong sales performance and its substantial market share (Statista, 2019).

Price: Coca-Cola employs sophisticated price differentiation strategies to meet the requirements of different market segments. By setting prices per market demands and the pricing tactics of its competitors, Coca-Cola effectively captures a share of the market and maintains profitability. Coca-Cola's strategic strategy, along with its intermittent use of higher prices, strengthens its position as a leading force in the business, frequently outperforming rival products. Finally, the company needs to take into consideration parameters such as market opportunities, growth rate, and geographic segmentation before the price is put in place. Nevertheless, while Coca-Cola is considered an oligopoly where there are few sellers and a large number of buyers, the dominants, Pepsi and Coca-Cola, have allied to ensure a price balance. It should be noted that the industry adopted various

pricing policies for their respective product items since the company has a wide range of competition although it has related production and demand costs (Coca-Cola, 2017).

Place: Distribution networks play a major role in the market penetration strategy of Coca-Cola while ensuring extensive availability in different parts of the world. Coca-Cola uses an efficient and organized system to carry out distribution networks for Fast Moving Customers' Goods (FMCG), where the distribution process starts with producers and ends with consumers, thereby touching the areas in almost all retail and big markets globally (Panagiotopoulou 2018).

Figure 3: FMCG sample (Flat World, 2017)

Although there may be several sales models in the market landscape, Coca-Cola still persists in making combinations of all intermediates, wholesales, retailers, and brokers in order to maintain and build the most efficient marketing channels globally, covering the wants of consumers such as product variety, delivery and waiting time, spatial convenience, and service backup. It is important to note that the distribution networks of Coca-Cola are so effective that they have eroded smaller production units of similar products (Panagiotopoulou, 2018).

Promotion: Coca-Cola brand-customer engagement and positioning efforts are integral to an extensive promotional campaign. The company utilizes a wide array of strategies, ranging from traditional advertising methods to customized campaigns using cultural icons and influencers, in order to engage customers. (Raghavendra & Renuka, 2018). Corporate social responsibility efforts further enhance brand awareness by stressing ethical business practices and environmental sustainability. The given way of advertising is interactive, as customers could be convinced to patronize the company's product. Finally, yet essential, is the fact that Coca-Cola adopts the strategy of push and pull by bringing an exceptional initiative strategy to both retailers and distributors to carry out the promotion of brand awareness. Particularly,

the industry accepts promotional sales to retailers as well as product price allowances and discounts among its distributors (Panagiotopoulou, 2018).

6.0 CONCLUSION

The evolution of Coca-Cola from the time it was established in 1886 to its present domination as the global beverage industry points out a narrative of flexibility, ingenuity, and strategic excellence. Coca-Cola with its portfolio has carried out techniques that will continue to help reshape the company for them to keep on striving in a change in the market due to technological advancement, demand shift, and intense competition among beverages industries. The company has successfully established itself as the leading brand as a result of imposing strategies in market penetration, segmentation, targeting, and position (STP), as well as the marketing mix which consists of the 4P. The company is dedicated to bringing about customer happiness and fostering innovation to thrive and adapt to change in the beverage market.

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